

15 cm above the ground 25 d after planting. Pruned hills flowered 1 wk later than nonpruned hills. Yield and percentage of seed set are presented in

the table.

Yields of A lines with pruned and nonpruned B lines were not significantly different. Seed yields of A line were

equal in 4:1, 3:1, 2:1, and 5:1 row ratios, and significantly superior to those at 6:1 and 1:1. A line seed set was high with 1:1 row ratio and low with 6:1. □

Seed yield and seed set in Zhen Shan 97 A line with different planting ratios. Coimbatore, India, 1986 summer.

A:B ratio	A line seed set ^a (%)				A line seed yield ^b				Mean yield (g/m ²)	% over 1:1
	B line pruned	B line nonpruned	Mean	Compared with 1:1	B line pruned		B line nonpruned			
					Yield (g/m ²)	% over 1:1	Yield (g/m ²)	% over 1:1		
1:1	19.3	18.5	18.9	100.0	49.5	100.0	45.6	100.0	47.5	100.0
2:1	18.8	17.9	18.4	97.4	61.6	124.4	55.7	122.1	58.6	123.4
3:1	16.9	16.5	16.7	88.4	62.4	126.1	58.2	127.6	60.3	126.9
4:1	17.4	15.8	16.6	87.8	64.3	129.9	57.6	126.3	60.9	128.2
5:1	15.5	14.1	14.8	78.3	60.5	122.2	55.3	121.3	57.9	121.9
6:1	13.6	12.8	13.2	69.8	56.5	114.1	51.2	112.3	53.8	113.3
Mean	16.9	15.9	16.4	86.8	59.1	119.4	53.9	118.2	56.5	118.9
% over nonpruned	103.0	100.0	—	—	—	109.6	—	100.0	—	—
LSD	—	—	1.6	—	—	—	—	—	4.3	—

^aSeed set: between A and B ratios = significant at 5% level; between B line pruned and nonpruned = not significant. ^bSeed yield: between A and B ratios = significant at 1% level; between B lines pruned and nonpruned = not significant.

Varietal differences in seed longevity

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We studied seeds of 32 rice varieties (8 dwarf ponlais; 12 dwarf indicas, and 12 tall indicas) under adverse storage conditions.

Seed samples (3 per variety) were thoroughly dried in the sun after Nov harvest and kept in thin cloth bags in ambient conditions. Germination percentages were recorded monthly Mar-Sep, with relative humidity and atmospheric temperature. (Seeds were germinated in petri dishes on moist blotting paper for 6 d.)

Varieties were classified on the basis of germination percentages:

Highly resistant = more than 80% germination.

Moderately resistant = germination 40-80%.

Weakly resistant = germination less than 40%.

The ponlai group appears to be highly susceptible to adverse storage conditions (see table). By Jun, ponlai varieties had

Resistance of rice varieties to loss of viability in storage. Hooghly, West Bengal, India.

Rice group	Varieties		
	Weakly resistant	Moderately resistant	Strongly resistant
Dwarf ponlais	Taichung 65 Kalimpong-I ^a Kalimpong-II ^a Tainan 3 Kaohsiung 68 Chianung 242 Chia 242 × CI 9155 IR60-1241 ^b		
Dwarf indicas	TN1 × Taichung 65	Taichung Native I IR8-178-3-1 IR4-67-2-3 IR4-90-2	IR9-60 IR8-288-3 IR8-64-3-1 IR8-190-1 IR5-47-2 IR5-114-3 IR4-263-1-2
Tall indicas	Churnakati Badkalamkati 65	NC1626 Nagrasail	FR43B OC1393 Kumargore Tilakkachari Ramsail SR26B Bhasamanik Bankura 517

^aSelection from ponlai. ^bWith ponlai-lie plant type.

become unsuitable for sowing. Among the tall indicas, short-duration Churnakati and Badkalamkati 65 were much weaker than long-duration

varieties. The long-duration local varieties also have strong dormancy.

Even though high-yielding dwarf varieties have short duration and mostly

weak or no dormancy, their storage life varied widely. Viability appears to be controlled by genetic factors; dwarf indica TN1/Taichung 65 lost viability very quickly.

In general, the gradual fall of seed viability was due to the increase in relative humidity (58% to 85%), and in temperature (26 to 31°C). □

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CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Urea hydrolysis in oxidized and reduced flooded soil

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We studied urea hydrolysis in oxidized and reduced soil systems in a controlled laboratory setup (Fig. 1). Soil was an Oxisol, kaolinitic clay (Typic Haplorthox) with pH 5.2, 1.72% organic C, 0.13% N, and CEC 15.5 meq/ 100 g. It contained 56.2% clay, 11.9% silt, and 31.9% sand.

Four hundred grams of 2 mm air-dried soil (oven dry weight basis) and 1,600 ml of water were placed into a 2-liter conical flask, stirred continuously with a magnetic stirrer, and incubated in the dark at 25 °C. Stable soil redox conditions and pH were obtained by continuously purging the soil suspension with 99.9% O₂ (for oxidized conditions) or 99.9% N₂ gas (for reduced conditions) for about 30 d before adding urea. Duplicate flasks were run for urea and no N treatments.

Urea was applied at 200 mg N/ kg soil and the contents of the flasks stirred continuously, purging either with O₂ or N₂ gas. Duplicate 25-ml aliquots of soil suspensions were removed 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, and 7 d after adding urea. The aliquots were used to determine oven-dry soil weight and urea N.

The oxidized soil suspension was extracted with KCl-PMA solution having a final concentration of 2M. The

reduced soil suspension was extracted by preflushing the bottles with N₂; O₂-free KCl-PMA solution also was used for

extraction. The supernatant solution of the reduced soil samples was filtered under a N₂ atmosphere. The unhydrolyzed urea recovered in the KCl-PMA extracts was determined colorimetrically immediately after extraction.

1. Schematic of experimental setup used to oxidize or reduce soil in the laboratory. Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge, USA, 1988.